

Effect of Planting Density and Fertilizer Source on Growth and Yield of Watermelon (*Citrullus Lanatus L.*) in Sudan Savanna of Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Field experiments were conducted at the Fadama Teaching and Research farm at Jega of Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aliero (lat. 12° 12.99' N; long. 4° 21.21' E; 197m above sea level) during 2021/2022 dry season. The aim was to study the effect of planting density and organic and inorganic fertilization on growth and yield of watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*). The treatments consisted of 5 planting densities (40,000, 26,667, 20,000, 17,778 and 13,333 plants per hectare; achieved at 50 x 50cm, 50 x 75cm, 50 x 100cm, 75 x 75cm and 75 x 100cm, respectively) and two levels of different fertilizer sources (NPK 15:15:15 and cow dung) plus untreated control, each was designed to supply the recommended Nitrogen dose of 120kg Nha⁻¹. The treatments were laid out in a Randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. The plot size was 4x3m (12m²) with 1.5m space between blocks and 1m between plots. The results of the study revealed that growth and yield parameters such as vine length, number of leaves, shoot dry weight, crop growth rate, relative growth rate, mean fruit diameter, mean fruit weight, number of fruits per plant, fruit yield (tha⁻¹) were higher with the application of either NPK or cow dung; as well as planting densities of 40,000, 26,677 and 13,333 in both locations. Interaction showed that all the planting densities attained maximum growth with the application of NPK fertilizer. It could be concluded that, the application of either cow dung or NPK fertilizer resulted in the growth and yield attributes of watermelon, but NPK recorded superior performance among the fertilizers, while the least fresh fruit yield was by untreated control.

Keywords: Watermelon, Planting, Density, Fertilization, Growth, Yield and Jega.

1. INTRODUCTION

Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*Thumb) is a member of the Cucurbitaceae family. It is believed to have originated from the Kalahari and Sahara deserts in Africa (Jarret *et al.*, 1996). Watermelon is now spread to all tropical and subtropical regions of the world and mostly grown for its fresh juicy flesh. In Nigeria, watermelon cultivation was originally confined to the drier savanna regions of the North, but is now gradually gaining ground in the southern parts of the country (Anon, 2006). Cultivation is mostly done in tropical and subtropical areas of the world for its vegetable and large edible fruits parts (Schippers, 2000) which are used in preparation of juice and salads. The fruits are excellent sources of nutrients, anti-oxidants, vitamin-c, flavonoids, carotenoids including lycopene (Peckens-Veazieet *al.*, 2006; Fassa, 2010) which are essential for optimal health in humans. It prefers temperature between 25°C to 35°C for optimum growth, and is grown under wide range of soil types with good drainage. Non saline sandy loam or silt loam soils with pH of 5.5 to 7.0 are preferred.

The major areas of watermelon production in the world as of 2017 are China, Iran, Turkey, Brazil and United State (Wikipedia, 2013). In the Triennium 2015-17, global production of the crop is estimated at 106,384 million tons

cultivated on 3.475 million hectares (yield of 30.6 tons per hectare) (Wikipedia, 2013). China topped the list of highest producers, producing almost 68% of global watermelon production for that year (Wikipedia 2013). As of 2017 watermelon accounted for 5.4% of harvested area devoted to vegetable production contributing 5% to world watermelon production in Africa. Currently, Africa is the third producer of watermelon in the world (Anonymous, 2019).

The demand of watermelon (*Citrillus lanatus*) is on the increase due to the continued awareness of its nutritional and health benefits. Watermelon is a heavy feeder of nutrients especially nitrogen (Schippers, 2000). But its supply is low because certain factors that militate against the production of the crop. The use of organic manure constitutes a constraint to farmers, because of its bulkiness, cost of transportation and handling. This type of problem is solved through the use of inorganic fertilizer. Generally, excessive amounts of inorganic fertilizers are applied to vegetables in order to achieve a higher and maximum value of growth (Dauda et al., 2008). Moreover, the use of inorganic fertilizer alone may cause problems to human health and the environment (Aisha et al., 2007). However, the use of inorganic fertilizer by local farmers is limited by its scarcity, cost and untimely availability. Farmers in Savannah agro ecological zone of Nigeria depend on inappropriate planting density in the production of watermelon which does not give high yield and this affects the production of watermelon. However, the used of appropriate planting density will improve the production of watermelon in Savannah agro ecological zone. The aim of this study is to determine the growth and yield of watermelon produced using different fertilizers and under different planting densities in the study area.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted in Teaching and Research Farm of the Kebbi State University of Science and Technology (KSUSTA) Aliero located in Jega, Kebbi State, Nigeria (lat. 12°12.99' N; long. 4° 21.90'E; Alt 197m) during 2019/20 and 2020/21 dry seasons. The area has a long dry season that is characterized by cool dry air (Harmattan) that prevails from November to February; and hot dry air extending from March to May. The cropping history of the site showed that the location was used for cultivation of vegetable and cereal crops. The treatments consist of five (5) plant population densities 40,000, 26,667, 20,000, 17,778 and 13,333 plants ha⁻¹, corresponding to 50 x 50cm, 50 x 75cm, 50 x 100cm, 75 x 75cm and 75 x 100cm, respectively; and two (2) fertilization levels; cow dung, NPK and the untreated control. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications. Variety (Local cultivar) of watermelon Kaolack was sourced from the local market in Aliero.

The experimental site was ploughed and harrowed to obtain good tilt. The land was leveled and constructed into seed beds; a water channel was constructed to facilitate free and efficient water movement and uniform distribution on the plots. The plot size was 4 x 3m (12m²). Space measuring 1.5m was left between blocks and 0.5m between plots. The net plot area consisted of the two middle rows (2.5 x 1.0m = 2.5 m²).

Irrigation was done at 3-5 days interval depending on the crop's need. Weeds were controlled manually using hand hoe at 3 and 6 weeks after sowing (WAS). All the data collected was subjected to analysis of variance using ANOVA and the difference among the treatment means was compared using Duncan new multiple range test (DNMRT) at 5% level of significance.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Soil Physical and Chemical Properties of Experimental Site:

Physical and chemical properties of soils of study location prior to the experiments are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Physical and chemical properties of experimental sites soil during 2019/2020 dry session.

	2021	2022
0–30cm depth		
Particles size Analysis		
Ph	6.60	6.11
Organic Carbon %	1.04	0.87
Organic Matter %	1.79	2.01
Total N %	0.084	0.093
P mg/kg	0.93	1.05
Ca (Cmol/kg)	0.50	0.78
Na Cmol/kg	0.52	0.62
Mg Cmol/kg	0.80	0.74
K Cmol/kg	1.95	2.56
CEC Cmol/kg	8.40	8.94
Sand %	63.3	61.7
Silt %	24.9	28.2
Clay %	11.8	10.1

3.2 Chemical composition of cow dung

Chemical compositions of Cow dung manure prior to the experiments is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Chemical Composition of cow dung (CD)

Parameters	Cow dung	
	2021	2022
O. C (g kg ⁻¹)	4.13	4.09
p ^H	7.60	7.20
T. N (mg kg ⁻¹)	1.02	1.08
Na (mg kg ⁻¹)	155	175
K (mg kg ⁻¹)	3800	3650
Ca (mg kg ⁻¹)	0.85	0.96
P (mg kg ⁻¹)	4.51	4.34

3.3 Response to planting density

The experiment showed (Table 3 and 4) that vine length, number of leaves; shoot dry weight, Relative growth rate, Days to 50% flowering and Numbers of fruits per plant of watermelon were not significantly increased with the increased planting density. During 2021 trial, planting density of 40,000pha⁻¹, 13,333pha⁻¹ and 20,000pha⁻¹ recorded statistically similar and higher length of vine while the shortest length of vine was recorded by planting density of 17,778pha⁻¹ and 26,667pha⁻¹. The non-significant treatment effect showed that vine length, number of leaves, shoot dry weight, Relative growth rate, Days to 50% flowering and Numbers of fruits per plant of watermelon were not influenced by spacing. This is not in conformity with the observation made by Dean *et al.* (2004) who observed that vegetative parameters increased with an increase in spacing of watermelon. This work however disagrees with the earlier findings of Edelstein and Sabo *et al.* (2013) who recommended high plant density for more fruit production per unit area. The reason may be that dense spacing design increases competition for water, nutrient and light which result in inadequate vegetative growth and yield.

A significant treatment effect on the Fruit weight per plant and Mean Fruit diameters showed (Table 5) that a higher value in both 2021 and 2022 trial could be achieved from planting density of 13,333pha⁻¹. These results are in agreement with the findings of Ban *et al.* (2006) who reported that the spacing has positive effect on growth and yield. These results also corroborated with the finding of Sabo *et al.* (2013) who reported an increase in watermelon vine length with an increase in spacing. Crop growth weight and Yield of watermelon were higher at planting density of 40,000pha⁻¹ was observed (Table 4 and 6), probably due to less competition for nutrients, water and space enjoyed by watermelon with lower population densities (Ilupeju *et al.*, 2011). The results suggest that decreased population density increased the average fruit yield of watermelon in this study. The findings are similar to those by Sabo *et al.* (2013).

3.4 Response to Fertilization

Fertilization is among the various agronomic practices that influences growth and yield of watermelon. Balanced nutrient management significantly increased watermelon yield. Organic manures supply nutrients as well as improve the soil physical and chemical conditions. Fertilizers (organic and inorganic) play important role in enhancing vegetative growth, starch synthesis as well as translocation (Silvia *et al.*, 2007). Vine lengths, Number of leaves, shoot dry weight Crop growth weight and Numbers of fruits per plant of watermelon (Table 3, 4 and 5) were higher with the application of NPK followed by cow dung. The enhancement of growth characters of watermelon may be attributed to increase in vegetative growth as effected by fertilizer. This agreed with the report of Messiaen (1992) that watermelon responds well to fertilizer application due to the soil enrichment with plant nutrients from the applied fertilizer. This nutrient availability is precursor to the promotion of root and vegetative growth (John *et al.*, 2014). Increase in fruit weight and yield (Table 5 and 6) can be attributed to the ability of fertilizer sources to promote vigorous growth resulting in increased meristematic and physiological activities. The increase in meristematic and physiological activities in plant due to abundant supply of plant nutrients led to the synthesis of more assimilates, which is used in producing fruits. On the other hand, the performance of cow dung in this study was in agreement with Adenawoda and Adejoro (2005) who reported that cow dung contained organic carbon, nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus, calcium and magnesium which is released into the soil upon decomposition and mineralization of the manure, and that depletion of soil organic matter under intensive cropping can be amended by proper addition of cow dung into the soil.

The significant effect of fertilization on Numbers of fruits per plant, Fruit weight per plant, Fruit diameters, Numbers of harvestable fruits and Yield of watermelon is an indication that yield components are under the influence of fertilization. Higher number of fruits was recorded with the application of NPK followed by cow dung. The earlier reason adduced for the observation in the growth parameters may also have been responsible for that in the yield parameters. This is because the yield components followed a similar trend with the growth parameters. The fruit weight per hectare using NPK resulted in greater yield than cow dung while the control recorded the lowest value. This could be attributed to its ability to maintain more favorable physical conditions of the soil and release of nutrients to plant in a balanced manner. Soil

amendment using NPK or cow dung has been reported to improve soil conditions and enhance plant growth through replenishment of soil nutrients (Elfediyet *et al.*, 2017).

3.5 Interaction

The significant interaction between the planting density and fertilization on Yield of watermelon (Table 7) indicated that the method of reducing plant density and the use of NPK fertilizer above poultry manure and cow dung could be practiced to increase marketable watermelon fruit size per plant (Ban *et al.*, 2006). The interaction shows that, in 2021 trial higher yield was obtained from the application of NPK fertilizer when combined with the planting density of 40,000 pha^{-1} while in 2022 trial, higher yield was obtained from the application of NPK fertilizer when combined the planting density of 40,000 pha^{-1} . This showed that, there is positive impact of NPK and manure on the growth and yield of watermelon, which highlights the importance of nutrient availability. NPK, being a balanced chemical fertilizer, provides readily available nutrients that are crucial for plant development. Manure also boosts crop growth due to its organic matter content, which improves soil structure and moisture retention. Similar study was carried out by da Silva *et al.*, (2016) on watermelon where NPK and organic fertilizer enhanced growth and yield.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, it could be concluded that, the application of NPK fertilizer or cow dung resulted in high growth and yield attributes of Watermelon, but NPK fertilizer recorded superior performance among the fertilizers, while the least yield was by untreated control. However, 40,000 pha^{-1} , 22,667 pha^{-1} out-yielded other planting densities.

5. RECOMMENDATION

From the findings of the study, the following recommendations could be made:

1. Application of either NPK fertilizer or cow dung could be adopted for higher watermelon fruit yield in the study area.
2. Planting density 40,000 pha^{-1} , 22,667 pha^{-1} could be considered since it recorded superior performance among the other planting density in the study area.

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